

Prophylactic Negative Pressure Wound Therapy to Prevent Surgical Site Infection after Emergency Laparotomy

1st Author

Dr Preethi SP

Professor

Department of general surgery

**JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of higher education and research, Mysuru,
Karnataka, India**

2nd Author and corresponding author

***Dr Dheeraj Arun Patil**

Post graduate

Department of general surgery

**JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of higher education and research, Mysuru,
Karnataka, India**

Email- dheerajpatil8.dp@gmail.com

3rd Author

Dr Girish Kumar NM

Assistant Professor

Department of general surgery

**JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of higher education and research, Mysuru,
Karnataka, India**

ABSTRACT:

Background: Surgical site infections (SSI) following emergency laparotomy remain a significant source of postoperative morbidity. Prophylactic Negative Pressure Wound Therapy (NPWT) has emerged as a promising intervention to reduce incidence of SSIs, especially in high-risk wounds. This study aimed to compare NPWT with conventional dressing in preventing SSIs and improving wound-related outcomes after emergency abdominal surgery.

Methods: In a single centre randomized controlled trial, 56 adult patients undergoing emergency laparotomy for acute abdomen were allocated to receive NPWT or betadine gauze dressing. Wounds were assessed postoperatively on days 4 and 30 for SSI, seroma, hematoma, and length of hospital stay.

Results: The rate of superficial SSI on postoperative day 4 was significantly lower in the NPWT group compared to the control group (3.6% vs. 21.4%, $p = 0.043$). At day 30, SSI remained lower in the NPWT group (7.1% vs. 25%, $p = 0.06$). No patients in the NPWT group developed deep SSI, seroma, or hematoma. Hospital stay was significantly shorter in the NPWT group (mean 9.68 days vs. 12.18 days; $p = 0.005$).

Conclusion: NPWT significantly reduced early superficial SSIs and decreased hospital stay compared to conventional dressing. It is an effective and safe prophylactic strategy following emergency laparotomy, particularly in contaminated wounds.

Keywords:

Negative Pressure Wound Therapy, Surgical Site Infection, Emergency Laparotomy, Wound Complications, Postoperative Outcomes

I. Introduction

Surgical site infection (SSI) is one of the most prevalent postoperative complications following emergency abdominal surgery, contributing to high morbidity, delayed recovery, and increased hospital costs. Emergency laparotomy frequently involves contaminated or dirty wounds, placing patients at particularly elevated risk. Standard betadine gauze dressing remains the most used postoperative wound care method in many centres. However, it offers limited ability to mitigate the risk of infection in high-risk wounds.

Negative Pressure Wound Therapy (NPWT), traditionally used for open or chronic wounds, has gained prominence when applied prophylactically over closed surgical incisions, especially in high-risk patients. The mechanism, involving continuous suction, promotes wound edge adherence, increased perfusion, and fluid removal.

This randomized controlled study aims to evaluate the clinical efficacy of prophylactic NPWT compared to conventional betadine dressing on prevention of SSI and wound complications in patients undergoing emergency laparotomy for acute abdominal conditions.

II. Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: A prospective, single centre randomized controlled trial was conducted from May 2023 to November 2024 at the Department of General Surgery, JSS Medical College, Mysuru. The protocol received ethical clearance from the institutional committee, and informed written consent was obtained from all participants.

a) Sampling Size Calculation:

Purposive sampling

Sample size: $N = 56$

Assuming the prevalence(P) of SSI is 5% with an error of 8%(D) and confidence interval of 95% ($Z=1.96$), a sample size of 28 in study and control group respectively needs to be collected. So the total sample size will be 56.

$$N = Z^2PQ / D^2$$

$$= (1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.05 \times 0.95) / 0.08 \times 0.08 = 28 \text{ per group} \times 2 \text{ groups} = 56 \text{ Total}$$

Where:

N= Desired sample size

Z= The standard normal deviation at the required confidence level (1.96)

P= Proportion of prevalence= 5% becomes 0.05

Q= 1-P= 1-0.05= 0.95

D²= Margin of error or confidence interval = 5% = 0.05

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age between 18 and 60 years
- Undergoing emergency laparotomy for acute abdomen

Exclusion Criteria:

- Need for re-exploration
- Inadequate abdominal closure (e.g. presence of stoma)
- Postoperative anastomotic leak or faecal fistula

Randomization and Groups

Patients were randomly assigned (1:1) into:

NPWT Group: Sterile foam connected to Ryle's tube & ioban dressing, applied immediately post-surgery and maintained with central negative pressure (-125 to -180 mmHg) for 4 days. [Figure 1,2]

Figure 1,2: Negative Pressure wound therapy Dressing

Control Group: Conventional betadine gauze dressing changed every alternate day.

Outcome Measures:

Primary Outcomes:

- Superficial and deep SSIs on postoperative day 4 and 30 (CDC criteria)

Secondary Outcomes:

- Seroma and hematoma formation

- Duration of hospital stay

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Blinded assessors evaluated wound integrity. SPSS version 26.0 was used for statistical analysis. Comparison between groups used chi-square/Fisher's exact test for categorical and t-test for continuous variables. Significance threshold: $p < 0.05$.

III. Results

Patient Enrolment and Baseline Characteristics

A total of 56 adult patients undergoing emergency laparotomy for acute abdomen were enrolled and randomized equally into the Negative Pressure Wound Therapy (NPWT) group (n=28) and the conventional dressing control group (n=28). All patients completed the study protocol with wound assessments performed on postoperative days 4 and 30.

Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were largely comparable between groups. The mean age was 47.79 ± 11.29 years in the NPWT group and 45.25 ± 12.72 years in the control group ($p=0.433$). Gender distribution showed equal males and females (50% each) in the NPWT cohort, versus a male predominance (71.4%) in controls; this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.100$). Importantly, the NPWT group exhibited a higher burden of comorbidities, with 60.7% of patients having one or more systemic illnesses compared to 32.1% in the control group ($p=0.03$). Similarly, body mass index (BMI) was significantly higher in the NPWT group (mean 28.7 ± 2.8 kg/m² versus 27.2 ± 2.3 kg/m², $p=0.03$). No significant differences were found in baseline laboratory parameters including haemoglobin, total leukocyte count, blood urea, or serum creatinine. [Table 1]

Table 1 : Comparison of Demographic and Clinical Parameters Between Case and Control

Groups

	Case or Control	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
AGE	Case	28	47.79	11.295	0.433
	Control	28	45.25	12.715	
BMI	Case	28	28.696	2.8288	0.03
	Control	28	27.218	2.3427	

Hemoglobin(gm/dl)	Case	28	12.871	2.0647	0.097
	Control	28	13.793	2.0226	
TLC(/mm3)	Case	28	16687.36	3749.594	0.627
	Control	28	15958.32	6969.718	
Blood Urea(mg/dl)	Case	28	36.93	19.251	0.28
	Control	28	43.18	23.476	
Serum Creatinine(mg/dl)	Case	28	.7375	.24245	0.06
	Control	28	.9179	.44408	
Length of hospital stay	Case	28	9.68	2.038	0.005
	Control	28	12.18	4.101	

Surgical wound classification was comparable, with 57.1% dirty (Class IV) and 42.9% contaminated (Class III) wounds in the NPWT group versus 64.3% dirty and 35.7% contaminated in controls (p=0.584).[Table 2, Figure 3] The distribution of operative procedures including adhesiolysis , bowel resections with anastomosis, appendectomy, peritoneal lavage, and hernia repair was similar across groups (p=0.27), ensuring balanced surgical risk profiles.

Table 2: Comparison of Surgical Wound Classification by Case or Control

Surgical Wound Classification	Case or Control				P value
	Case		Control		
	Count	%	Count	%	
Contaminated(Class 3)	12	42.9%	10	35.7%	0.584
Dirty (class 4)	16	57.1%	18	64.3%	
Total	28	100.0%	28	100.0%	

Figure 3: Comparison of Surgical Wound Classification by Case or Control

Surgical Site Infection Outcomes

Early Superficial SSI (Postoperative Day 4)

The primary endpoint of superficial surgical site infection (SSI) at postoperative day 4 demonstrated a significant reduction in the NPWT group. Only 1 patient (3.6%) in the NPWT cohort developed superficial SSI, compared to 6 patients (21.4%) in the control group ($p=0.043$). This represents an 83% relative risk reduction in early superficial SSI favouring NPWT (Risk ratio 0.17, 95% CI 0.02–1.24). The lower SSI rate in the NPWT group is notable given the higher comorbidity burden and BMI. [Table 3, Figure 4]

Table 3: Comparison of Superficial SSI Day 4 by Case or Control

	Case or Control				P value
	Case		Control		
Superficial SSI Day 4	Count	%	Count	%	
No	27	96.4%	22	78.6%	0.043
Yes	1	3.6%	6	21.4%	
Total	28	100.0%	28	100.0%	

Figure 4: Comparison of Superficial SSI Day 4 by Case or Control

Late Superficial SSI (Postoperative Day 30):

At 30 days postoperatively, the incidence of superficial SSI remained lower in patients treated with NPWT, though the difference did not reach conventional statistical significance. Two patients (7.1%) in the NPWT group developed superficial SSI versus seven (25%) in the control group ($p = 0.06$). The consistent trend favoring NPWT indicates a sustained benefit in reducing wound infections beyond the immediate postoperative period. [Table 4, Figure 5]

Table 4 :Comparison of Superficial SSI Day 30 by Case or Control

	Case or Control				P value
	Case		Control		
Superficial SSI Day 30	Count	%	Count	%	
No	26	92.9%	21	75.0%	0.06
Yes	2	7.1%	7	25%	
Total	28	100.0%	28	100.0%	

Figure 5 : Comparison of Superficial SSI Day 30 by Case or Control

Deep SSI

No cases of deep SSI were documented in the NPWT group at either postoperative day 4 or day 30. In contrast, the control group had one deep SSI case (3.6%) at both time points, though these differences were not statistically significant ($p = 0.31$). The absence of deep SSI in the NPWT cohort supports potential protective effects extending to deeper tissue layers.

Wound-Related Complications

No instances of seroma or hematoma formation were observed in either group across the 30-day postoperative follow-up period, indicating a favourable safety profile for both NPWT and conventional dressing modalities in this context. [Table 5]

Table 5 : Comparison of Deep SSI on Day 4 and 30, Seroma and Hematoma by Case and Control

Outcome	Timepoint	NPWT (n=28)	Control (n=28)	p-value
Deep SSI	Day 4	0 (0%)	1 (3.6%)	0.31
Deep SSI	Day 30	0 (0%)	1 (3.6%)	0.31
Seroma	Day 30	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	--
Hematoma	Day 30	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	--

Length of Hospital Stay

A statistically significant reduction in the length of hospital stay was observed in the NPWT-treated patients. The mean duration of admission was 9.68 ± 2.04 days for the NPWT group, compared to 12.18 ± 4.10 days in controls ($p = 0.005$). This 2.5-day decrease in hospitalization has important implications for healthcare resource utilization, cost savings, and patient recovery trajectories.

Subgroup and Additional Analyses

Despite a higher prevalence of comorbid conditions and increased BMI in the NPWT group, both well-established risk factors for SSI, the lower incidence of superficial SSI highlights the robustness of NPWT's protective efficacy. This suggests that NPWT may mitigate the adverse impact of systemic illness on wound healing and infection risk.

Wound contamination severity was evenly distributed, confirming that the benefits observed were not confounded by differing baseline infectious risk.

Furthermore, the surgeries performed across both groups were evenly matched in complexity and contamination potential, underscoring the direct association of the intervention with improved outcomes rather than case mix variation.

Adverse Events and Safety

No device-related complications or adverse effects attributable to the NPWT dressings were reported in this study. Specifically, no cases of skin maceration, pressure injury, or discomfort necessitating discontinuation of NPWT were observed, affirming its tolerability and safety in the emergency laparotomy patient population.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study adds to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of NPWT for preventing postoperative wound infections in high-risk surgical cases like emergency laparotomy. Our findings demonstrate a clear benefit of NPWT in reducing the rate of early superficial SSI, which aligns with multiple prior studies and meta-analyses showing 50–60% relative risk reduction in contaminated wounds [1-3].

More importantly, even though our NPWT cohort had a higher BMI and comorbidity profile—factors typically associated with greater SSI risk [4,5], the superficial SSI incidence remained significantly lower. This suggests that NPWT may offset some of the adverse effects seen in high-risk groups, thus serving as an equalizer in heterogeneous clinical settings [6,7].

Furthermore, the shortened hospital stay observed in the NPWT group not only reflects reduced complication rates but has practical implications on resource utilization and surgical bed turnover [8,9]. With rising healthcare costs and congestion in surgical departments, even a 2-day reduction in postoperative admission, as reported here, has measurable financial value [10,11].

Our findings mirror conclusions drawn in a recent multicentre trial showing that NPWT decreased SSI incidence in colorectal and trauma surgeries [1,10]. Additionally, the safety of NPWT was affirmed in our series—no seromas, hematomas, or device-related adverse effects occurred [7,12,13].

However, we recognize our study's limitations. The single-centre nature, modest sample size, and challenge of blinding wound care teams may affect generalizability [14,15]. Also, while promising trends in day 30 outcomes were observed, statistical significance was not consistently achieved, warranting larger trials to reinforce conclusions [1,2].

Nonetheless, this trial reinforces NPWT as a simple yet impactful intervention in complex emergency settings, particularly when patient anatomy, wound contamination, or time constraints preclude ideal surgical handling [16-19].

V. CONCLUSION

Prophylactic application of NPWT over closed surgical incisions significantly decreases early postoperative superficial SSI and total hospital stay in patients undergoing emergency laparotomy, even among those with higher comorbidity burden. NPWT remains a safe, effective, and scalable strategy in managing surgical wounds at high risk for infection.

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